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Visioning for an Educational Institution: Conceptual & Methodological Issues

(Abstract)

Since the last few years, 'accreditation' became the buzz-word in the higher educational institutions of West Bengal. The process of accreditation, along with measuring the other parameters of educational standards of an institution, also takes into account the level of institutional foresight and accountability that is being reflected by the vision statement. Conceptually, vision is the 'desired future state' or the 'aspirations of the institution' which no institution can do without. It crystallizes not only the aims and objectives of the institutional operations but also assures its acceptability to all its stakeholders.

The concept and purpose of visioning is easy to understand, but is equally difficult to formulate through a consensus amongst the different stakeholder groups as unanimity among academicians in respect of educational issues is hard to come by. Moreover, the present educational atmosphere is plagued by suspicion, contradiction and conflict amongst academicians as well as the other stakeholder groups usually influenced by the trade unionized culture of West Bengal.

Thus, besides the hard task of documentation for accreditation, defining the vision statement through participation and consensus of various stakeholder groups is the real challenge. Being over-burdened with these, some of the institutions may simplify the process and come up with some platitudes or normative statements – that may ultimately prove to be fatal for the respective institution.

The present paper therefore, will first of all elaborate the conceptual dimensions of vision, visioning and its linkage with the strategic planning process. Finally, the paper will describe how the vision can be developed through the participation of the stakeholders.

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Visioning for an Educational Institution: Conceptual & Methodological Issues

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Introduction

Higher education in India is in a process of transformation nowadays. The impact of globalization and the transition of a mixed and protective economy to an open market economy have let loose a phase of turbulence (forces of change) in the educational atmosphere of both national and state levels. Educational scenario is now beset by competition, withdrawal or gradual reduction of Government grants and subsidies, financial deficits, entry of private players, appointment of part time and contractual faculties, etc. The credibility of the old principles and practices of education is further at stake with the loss of relevance of the traditional courses in the job market, opening up of correspondence and distance learning systems and the appearance of new technologies like computer and biotechnology. The threat of the entry of the multinationals in the higher education sector from 2005 onwards is a further setback to the existing problems. The impact of all these factors on the educational atmosphere of the country certainly put all academicians and educational institutions on high alert and there is a widespread concern to rejuvenate the educational fabric of the country on new lines of innovation and improvisation. In fact the National Policy on Education (NPE) and the Program of Action (POA), 1986 inter alia recommended for setting up of a council to assess and accredit educational institutions for their quality of education, participation and achievements, which would also encourage self-evaluation and self-improvement among institutions. Accordingly the University Grants Commission (UGC), under section 12 CCC of the UGC Act of 1956(3), established the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) on 16 September 1994 at Bangalore. This concern among academics for ensuring quality in higher education has been a source of strength and inspiration for NAAC. The council provides as much importance to the present performance of an institution as to its future goals and targets that the institution seeks to achieve. Thus, 'vision statement' receives special emphasis in NAAC's process of evaluation of the academic excellence and future progress of an institution. The present paper seeks to analyze the importance of 'vision statement' as a genuine revelation of an institution's basic objectives and goals that it sets for its own to get.

Institutional performance depends on several variables like the level of morale and motivation of its employees, work culture of the institution, resources – both physical and human, its technological inputs and infrastructure, etc. Unfortunately, many of these pre-conditions are lacking in the educational institutions of West Bengal. The state of educational institutions in India in general and West Bengal in particular is really deplorable since there is hardly any consensus among different stakeholders of the educational institutions to improve quality education. The educational atmosphere in West Bengal is fraught with frequent strikes, demonstrations, agitations, movements and campaigns as an embodiment of the political culture that exists here and the institutions are far away from their basic focus of educational missions and visions. The long run effect of this would certainly cost dear to the institutions as its scope to generate or secure funds from external agencies would narrow down considerably owing to the typical politicization of educational institutions in West Bengal. Educational institutions these days have become merely followers of political dictates taken less in the interest of academic progress and more for political pacification. Decisions, which may affect an institution's future, are often made politically, in isolation and among a clique of faculty and administrators having political homogeneity. Nobody here is really bothered about what is wrong in the system and how to rectify it. How then the institutes would assure their survival in the long run ?

The only solution of the aforesaid ailments of the educational institutions is to incorporate the process of strategic planning. Strategic planning refers to such a managerial function that is directed to achieve goals within a turbulent environment through efficient allocation of institutional resources. Simply, it refers to such a planning for the institution, which is focused on the external environment. According to Cope G. (1987, p.3),

“Strategic planning is an open systems approach to steering an enterprise over time through uncertain environmental waters. It is a proactive problem-solving behavior directed externally at conditions in the environment and a means to find a favorable competitive position in the continual competition for resources. Its primary purpose is to achieve success with mission while linking the institution’s future to anticipated changes in the environment in such a way that the acquisition of resources (money, personnel, staff, students, goodwill) is faster than the depletion of resources”

Strategic Planning : The Genesis of Vision :

Strategic planning seems to be necessary to cope with the turbulent external environment through efficient allocation of institutional resources. It primarily focuses on what the institution needs to do in the present to position itself favorably in the future. The process begins first with the identification of the salient strengths and weaknesses of the institution. Identification of the strengths and weaknesses of an institution is focused on the basic question ‘what does the institution have that it can build upon?’ Anything that an institution has that it can use as leverage such as a prominent location, reputation, values, technology, finances, physical plant, etc. would be the strength of an institution. The next stage comprises environmental scanning or a critical and detailed evaluation of the economic, demographic, political and technological changes to identify the possible opportunities and threats. At this stage, the focus should be on the economic shifts and policy changes of a nation, its technological advancement and social changes both in the family and in the society at large to ascertain job opportunities, trading facilities and other potential sectors of employment. In the third stage, the strengths are linked with the emerging opportunities arising resulting in a collective sense i.e., a vision of what the institution wants to do to become a distinctive one. After identifying the opportunities, there is a need to connect the strengths with the opportunities in order to obtain the “directions of travel”. Thus, directions to travel, viz., vision can be obtained through five ‘R’s i.e., Redirect, Reshape, Renew, Risk, and Reaffirmation (Cope, 1987, p.21). Vision provides conceptual glue and momentum, and illuminates shared purpose. Thus, the process of developing of a viable and visible vision is an outcome of the process of strategy formulation.

What is Vision ?

It would not be out of place to begin with some elementary statements on vision. Management author Tom Peters has identified a clear vision of the desired future state of the organization as an essential component of high performance. Widely-read organizational development author Warren Bennis identified a handful of traits that made great leaders great. Among them is the ability to create a vision. Further, it can be conceived as a *guiding image of success formed in terms of a contribution to society*. If a strategic plan is the "blueprint" for an organization's work, then the vision is the "artist's rendering" of the achievement of that plan. It is a description in words that conjures up a similar picture for each member of the group of the destination of the group's work together.

According to Cope (1987, p.39), “vision... is the future focus ... (that) grabs attention. Vision is the combination of strengths related to opportunities projected forward. Vision provides road maps that guide the implementation. Vision sets the agenda in context. Vision inspires, animates, and transforms mission into action. It is the conceptual glue. The right vision and key success factors sweep energy back and forth in subtle ways.”

Vision reflects the images of the future and originates from deliberate efforts to change. It should be attractive and promising so that people feel motivated to work towards achieving it. Effective visions usually depict the aspirations of the institutional members and motivate them to work for it. Visions also help to develop future focus and strategies of an institution to be pursued for a better tomorrow discarding old and outdated ones of the past. They also contain deeper images of an institution that people carry around them. It provides a common bond of unity of purpose and commitment to work together towards a shared and preferred future as like contracts and treatises.

Vision of an institution, to a great extent, is shaped by the values and beliefs of the authorities of the institution or the dominant coalition that makes decision on behalf of the stakeholders of an institution. For example, the employees of South Plains College have defined a vision statement which, according to them is "...a desired state and preferred future...a dream created out of personal and organizational values of how we would like South Plains College to be. Our vision statement ... provide direction for the college and inspires the college community to stretch beyond its present level of institutional effectiveness." The Vision Statement for Northeast Community College was developed in Spring 1996 by the students, faculty, staff, advisory committee representatives and the Board of Governors. Vision statement, as they have defined it "...is a futuristic look at the college in 10-15 years, including 1) the students and their needs, 2) the educational programs and services we will be offering, and 3) the requirements and support needed by the faculty and staff delivering the programs and services.

An institution's vision is the highest statement of aspirations of the institutional members that dedicates them to a tradition of service to their stakeholders as well as to the academic and administrative standards. The vision is invaluable for the institutional members because their commitment to it keeps everyone focused on accomplishing their purpose and goals. Also, vision statement directs the planning, the daily work, and the attitudes of the institutional members.

A vision statement is more connotative than denotative. It suggests and implies the vision rather than specifying it in the way that a mission statement specifies exactly how an enterprise is to be conducted. A vision statement leaves room for individual interpretation. The connotations are more important than what the words literally say.

What are the Characteristics of an Ideal Vision Statement ?

A vision statement should be realistic and credible, well articulated and easily understood, appropriate, ambitious, and responsive to change. It should orient the group's energies and serve as a guide to action. It should be consistent with the organization's values. In short, a vision should challenge and inspire the group to achieve its mission. The characteristics of vision can be summarized as under :

- ❖ It should be simple, clear, credible, optimistic and easily understandable by the people associated with an institution;
- ❖ It should be distant enough in time to accommodate dramatic changes - but at the same time, should be close enough to gain credibility of the institutional members;
- ❖ It should have the ability to create a sense of urgency among the institutional members;
- ❖ It should have been framed through a broad consensus and support from the institutional members.
- ❖ It should be able to motivate the institutional members and mobilize the resources required.
- ❖ It should be based on the future competitive aspirations instead of the limitations of the immediate circumstances.

- ❖ It should provide a shock of recognition that has the ability and intensity to derive attention and evoking resonating images
- ❖ It should remind people of the tough things that need doing and the reasons for them.
- ❖ It should elevate the aspirations of the institutional members and show them a brighter and more successful future for themselves if the institution could achieve it.
- ❖ It should ignite the energies and empower the institutional members to move forward together to achieve a shared purpose.
- ❖ It should center around people and provide directions for the future and pinpoint the direction for change
- ❖ It should have the capacity to divert energies and enthusiasms of the institutional members to the right direction and thereby enhance its performance
- ❖ It should be the dreams of the institutional members as well as an inspiration for all – the destination where everyone associated wants to go.
- ❖ It should have the power and passion to translate paper strategies into reality.
- ❖ It should incorporate the interests of all the stakeholders.

Why to Define Vision Statement ?

Though the vision statement is an outcome of the process of strategy formulation, vision serves a number of purposes for an educational institution. John Bryson, the author of *Strategic Planning for Public and Nonprofit Organizations*, states that typically, a vision is "more important as a guide to implementing strategy than it is to formulating it." This is because the development of strategy is driven by what you are trying to accomplish, your organization's purposes. A vision, however, is more encompassing. It answers the question, "What will success look like?" It is the pursuit of this image of success that really motivates people to work together.

Visioning may apparently appear to be vague and superfluous. However, the long-term benefits are substantial, viz., it encourages to think beyond the horizon, helps to maintain consistency in action, provides the direction and purpose, convince the stakeholders to initiate the required changes, promotes interest and commitment, promotes laser-like focus, encourages openness to unique innovative solutions, encourages and builds confidence, builds loyalty through involvement, assures efficiency and productivity. Also, vision has some major significance as described under :

Vision & Institutional Distinctiveness

To assure survival within a highly competitive market, an educational institution must have some distinguishing features - something of value that would provide it a unique identity or a sense of superiority over the other institutions in the locality. A distinct identity is necessary to attract students, better faculty or even grants and sanctions from the donor agencies. Institutional distinctiveness also serves as the basis of positioning an institution positively in the minds of the prospective students or parents and thus, acts as a fundamental tool in marketing its services. George Keller mentioned, "to think strategically is to look intensely at contemporary history and your institution's position in it and work out a planning process that actively confronts the historical movement, overcomes it, gets on top of it, or seizes the opportunities latent in it" (Keller, 1983). This statement is the essential prescription for positive positioning. It is essential for every institution to determine where it can best serve its clients and what activities will best position the institution as an integral and recognized asset to its community, i.e., what makes it distinctive. Institutional distinctiveness is actually an outcome of the vision. Only

a unique vision is sufficient to make an institution virtually distinctive in the minds of the prospective clients or stakeholder groups.

Vision & Performance Evaluation :

For the purpose of assessing the performance of an educational institution, one must, first of all identify the performance criteria – the basis on which performance would be measured. Several alternative indicators of performance are available like :

- ❖ Student enrollment
- ❖ Student retention
- ❖ Examination results
- ❖ Placement success of the ex-students
- ❖ Performance of the students in State or national level competitive examinations
- ❖ Student-faculty ratio
- ❖ Faculty credential improvements
- ❖ Addition of new courses
- ❖ Representation of the faculty in University/Regulatory agencies

Besides, indicators like physical facilities in the campus, quality of administrative processes, level of computerization, students' and faculty satisfaction, morale, institutional image, work culture, innovativeness, etc. are also performance indicators for educational institutions. While there is no dearth of performance criteria or indicators, which one or set of criteria should be the basis of measurement for a particular institution depends on its vision. 'Where does an institution want to be' viz., the vision would dictate which are the most important issues or critical success factors for a particular institution. In the absence of a clearly defined and communicated vision, comprehensive performance criteria and meaningful standards of performance cannot be designed for an institution. Without the road map, viz., the vision, the evaluation process will have no sound basis of asking the question 'How an institution is performing ?' Once the vision is framed, it would be easy to answer questions like : What should be the priorities of an institution ? What are the resources needed ? How the resources can be accumulated ? What shall be the timetable for accomplishment ? What is the linkage amongst the tasks ? How could we understand where we are now ?

Thus, a valid vision helps choosing or setting the most suitable criteria or indicators of performance. In this connection, it is to be noted that no single or uniform criteria can be used for performance measurement since the visions or the most desired futures are institution-specific.

Vision & Mission :

According to Johnson & Scholes, (1999, p. 13) mission refers to the 'Overriding purpose in line with the values or expectations of Stakeholders'. Thus, mission is a concise statement of the fundamental current and future purpose of a country, division, department or program. A mission statement answers the questions: "Why does our organization exist?" "What business are we in?" "What values will guide us?"

Vision refers to the "Desired future state : the aspiration of the organization". In other words, vision is a statement of an ideal future for an institution. A vision statement answers the question "What will success look like?" Thus, vision puts the mission statement to work by making it something that is shared by institutional members and is inspirational and clear enough to let people know what kind of decisions are appropriate within a particular institution.

Visioning : A Challenge for an Institution

Defining the vision statement would be a challenge for the top administrators of the educational institutions of West Bengal as this is an integral part of the process of accreditation. The task has two dimensions - defining the vision and generating a contagious enthusiasm throughout the institution in its favor. The vision statement of an educational institution should convey with it an obsession that can be perceived as a strategic direction. A vision statement, however nicely designed, would not bring in any significant change unless it is supplemented with a process of pooling the collective knowledge and commitment. In fact, creating a new vision requires a different mind-set associated with conventional strategic analysis. Visioning is actually creating possibilities that will stretch an institution to acquire new capabilities. It is alike creating competitive advantage through a detailed analysis of the institution's future rather than the past. Visioning could be considered as a process of self –discovery – a creative process to link up the strengths of an institution with the opportunities in the external environment

Defining the vision statement simply does not assure any significant change in an institution. Mere definition of vision, even cannot assure its adoption and implementation. However, during the process of defining it, the attention of the group gets focused on issues, which are supposed to be the core of attention for the institutional members. Besides, in this process, individuals who have a greater ability of lateral thinking or who already have thought a lot about the major directions of an institution can be isolated from among those who keep them busy in pleasing the top executive or the political bosses without having any serious concern about the overall development of the institution itself.

Visioning, under a congenial environment can be a fun, even exhilarating. Visioning can release the tensions of the moment and provide energy and direction for fundamental change. Vision-driven change is change with purpose. Visioning is merely a way to stimulate open-minded dialogue among a diverse group about future scenarios. If this dialogue does not lead to a vision of a desirable change, then there is no point of continuing the process. If those promoting change cannot forge a consensus for change, they will certainly fail in the change process itself. But beginning with visioning ensures that the institution will get in touch with its stakeholders and its environment and will be more responsive to their needs in the process.

What should be Avoided

Defining the vision is not sufficient. It is more important to assure its institution-wide adoption and this calls for an effective leadership inside the institution. The level of commitment of the employees to work together towards attaining a carefully articulated vision could assess the effectiveness of the leadership. However, due to the presence of trade unionism in a state like West Bengal, the responsibility for leadership is often delegated to the sub–units within the institution in the name of 'democratization'. In such situations, there are chances that the vision, in the hands of politically powerful but academically myopic leaders of the trade unions, becomes fragmented into territorial power struggles with extraordinary energies focused on trivial issues or personal agenda of sub-units. Hence, even the best vision may not produce any positive result in the hands of incapable leadership.

The vision must be consistent to the culture of a particular institution. Otherwise, there is a chance of the institution becoming distant, impersonal, threatening to the students and fearsome for the employees leading to distrust, anxiety, depression and loss of performance.

In most cases, trade union leaders, after gaining sufficient power and authority, are administering the educational institutions. They might have confusion between a vision statement and a slogan. A slogan, according the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary,

refers to a 'word or phrase that is easy to remember' and is 'used as a motto by a political party or in advertisements'. Thus, if the vision is considered as a slogan, it could never help to develop clear-cut strategies for the long-term survival of the institution.

Lack of vision is a common syndrome of the educational institutions in West Bengal. In fact, very few administrators would agree that they **should** divert their energies towards achieving a well-defined goal. Since there is no specific direction or goal, there exists an apparent agreement among the different stakeholder groups. The dominant coalitions viz., the faculty and the employees are exploiting the institutions to the maximum extent possible, not for any academic goal but for their self-interests. Under such a situation, an attempt to define a vision concretely and specifically for the interest of the institution may result into chaos. In fact the present generation of the academic elite tends to be rhetoric in delivering speeches and comments – though they are never specific. In most of the institutions, open criticism of the 'system' is a common feature. But, if the same critics are asked to suggest some constructive measures for the removal of the grounds of his/her criticism, conflict erupts. In the absence of any long-term vision, nobody knows or even bothers about 'where they are going'. Particularly the faculties and administrators are so much accustomed to their present level of tolerance to ambiguity that now they might resist the idea of having a vision or take it as lightly as possible.

It should be remembered that visioning is of the heart - not the head. The danger in crafting vision statements is that people can take them too literally. Language is used in two ways, connotative and denotative. The denotative meaning of a word is what it stands for; the connotative meaning is what it implies. In the process of developing vision statement, the attempt should be to disconnect what is presently going on from what the institution would like to be in future.

The Alliance for Nonprofit Management, (<http://www.allianceonline.org/>) has nicely mentioned, "Do not try to write a vision statement with a group. (Groups are great for many things, but writing is not one of them!). Ask one or two people to try drafting a vision statement based on the group's discussion, bring it back to the group, and revise it until you have something that your members can agree on and that your leaders share with enthusiasm.

Enemies of Visioning :

In the process of visioning, one should remain alert of the following enemies :

Tradition : Myopic academicians are strong defenders of the status quo. Naturally, they might resist the process of visioning as it is out of tradition.

Fear to be ridiculed : Some people never participate in any group process simply for the fear to be ridiculed. The facilitators must have sufficient maturity to bring them in action and involve them in the process of visioning.

Stereotypes of people, conditions, roles and governing councils : Stereotyping is a common perceptual error that leads to a total disregard towards the power of others.

Complacency of some stakeholders : Over satisfaction of some of the stakeholders may discourage them to participate in the process of visioning actively. In fact, it is difficult to activate them. Still, they should be taken into confidence.

Fatigued leaders : They are hard-core critics of anything in which they have no interest at present. Simply, they concentrate in finding flaws of any new initiative and hence, should be handled with great care and caution.

Short-term thinkers : They are more concerned about the present than the future. They have a lower emotional quotient and they believe in immediate or momentary satisfaction of needs. If they feel that the process of visioning will yield its results in the distant future, they may disassociate themselves from the process.

Silent spectators : Neither they are really harmful nor are they helpful for the process of visioning. They remain present – but never speak or actively participate in the process. It needs a lot of patience and enthusiasm to activate them to get any kind of assistance from them.

Creating a Vision : The Methodology

Ideally, vision should be incorporated at the time of founding an institution. However, most of the educational institutions operating in the contemporary society have been set up long back. By that time, it was not mandatory to declare and document a written vision statement and as such, very few institutions have been able to preserve the original visions of the founders. Whatever might be the case, an institution can define or redefine its vision anytime at the middle of its progress or at any interjunction when periodic assessment of the progress is being made by the institution as many of the old visions may simply have lost their relevance in the contemporary world. External pressures, like the process of accreditation, may sometimes force an institution to frame its vision.

Selecting the Participants

A survey of the literature available on the issue reveals that there exists no one best method of defining the vision that can be applied in all institutions. Different institutions have adopted different methods depending upon their internal and external environments. Theoretically, an institution should involve all the stakeholder groups like Governing Body Members, local administration, institutional authorities, faculty, non-teaching employees, students, guardians, alumni, local community, donor or investors, representatives of the affiliating university, suppliers, bankers, etc. in the process of visioning since vision affects everybody associated with an institution. External stakeholders can effectively contribute in describing external trends and their potential future impacts and the internal stakeholders can provide insight on how the institution may react. Thus, An active participation of all the stakeholders can generate more creative and innovative proposals linking the needs and aspirations of the diverse constituencies and focusing attention on the future educational programs. However, limiting resources like time, money and energy at the disposal of an institution might restrict the ability of an institution to involve everybody. Again, visioning is not an widely practiced activity and in reality, few can do it well – everybody cannot. Since each stakeholder group has its own interests, it is desirable to include selected representatives from all the various groups, of course at a reasonable proportion.

Within the highly politicalized environment of West Bengal, it might be a controversial task to find out an agreed-upon basis of selecting participants for the purpose of vision designing. Unless an agreed upon method of selecting participants is developed, those who selected might feel overburdened while those who have not been included may feel dejected. Practically, the task of vision defining calls for a set of skills in a participant, viz., an increased level of awareness, a greater familiarity with the institution, a greater level of commitment and involvement, ability to think creatively, foresightedness, language fluency, sense of value and impartiality in judgment, etc. Thus, one way of selecting participants might be to ask the respective tradeunion leaders to nominate their representatives for this purpose. Ideally, age, gender, caste, religion, political affiliation, proximity to leadership should be the criteria for selecting participants – otherwise, the process will not be able to deliver the desired results.

Structure of the Visioning Sessions

The structure of the visioning sessions may vary widely depending upon the culture, tradition, availability of time and other resources, etc. Some may adopt carefully managed focus groups involving homogeneous groups of stakeholders like the faculties

or administrators and use carefully worded scripts to generate specific outcomes. Others may use more informal gatherings of the local community or alumni who are not very much familiar with one another and much less involved in the day-to-day operations of the institution – but are more exposed to the external environment. Still other sessions may be designed employing open-ended future-search techniques to encourage unbounded creative thinking. In the beginning, there might be a feeling that only the creative people could vision – not everyone. However, it would be the duty of the facilitators to assure that everyone could participate, that there are some people who are very concrete and some people are very abstract, but they can all participate. Whatever their structure is, each session must include a broad range of institutional stakeholders and free expression of ideas. Also, the participants must be aware of what kind of output is intended from the session.

The Facilitators

To develop a vision quite a few number of meetings, conferences, sessions may be required and it is impossible for a single individual to handle all of them. Thus, a small group of facilitators is to be developed. The facilitators must understand that mere listening and cooperative skills are not sufficient in the visioning sessions, success actually depends on the participants showing respect for the diversity of the group. The facilitators must acquire skills like using the names of the participants, active listening, shared leadership, encouraging everyone to participate, summarizing the deliberations, avoiding assumptions or leading questions. Finally, facilitating and mentorship skills are the key determinants of success of a facilitator. Some important tips for the facilitators are mentioned below :

- ❖ Provide some background information before initiating a visioning session. People must know what they are supposed to do. For example, some sample vision statements of other institutions may be displayed to familiarize the participants with their task.
- ❖ In case the number of participants in a session is very large, divide them into few sub-groups and assign identical tasks and create a sense of competition among the groups. Finally, synthesize the contributions appreciating the group, which has contributed the best or highest number of ideas.
- ❖ Every participant in a group must get a chance to express himself /herself. In most cases, few people dominate the discussions and the facilitator in such cases must intervene. Also, enough time should be allotted for each session so that everyone could participate.
- ❖ Tasks or activities should be designed in such a manner so as to break all the preconceived notions, prejudices or suspicions of the participants. Participants should not feel that everything has been decided in advance, somewhere else and the meeting is only a formality to communicate them the final results.

Methods Adopted for Generating Ideas

(1) Small Group Meeting :

Small group meetings are perhaps the best tools for visioning as they can assure the assimilation of the hopes, aspirations, trends, and preferred futures of the participants. Carefully selected representatives of the different stakeholder groups of the institution may constitute such groups and the agenda for discussion would be the vision only. The meeting can take an hour or multiple hours to explore vision. Breaking into small groups for collecting information on what would be ideal vision sometimes helps to conceptualise vision better. The questionnaire method too can be resorted to get information from groups about what people think in respect of the vision. For example

questions can be put forward like how do you want your college to be different? What role do you want your institution to play to enhance the job potentials of your students? What will be the sources of fund in future? The objective of this method is to make people stretch their minds and experiment with different ways of thinking about what success means to them. Finally, all the other constituent groups would be asked to share their pictures on vision with each other. One person should facilitate the discussion and help the group to discuss what they mean and what they hope for. The focus in such meetings would be on areas of agreement, as well as different ideas that emerge. The goal is to find homogeneity in imaging the future directions.

(2) Brainstorming

Brainstorming is a way of generating a large number of ideas as quickly as possible as is needed in the process of visioning. It is by far the most widely used tool of generating creative ideas from a group (Placek, 1989) that had been developed in the 1940s and 1950s by an advertising executive Alex Osborn. Creating a vision through brainstorming begins with and relies heavily on intuition and dreaming. In these sessions, groups of stakeholders, either heterogeneous or homogeneous, are assembled to visualize and react on an anticipated future - such as the implications of demographic trends or future requirements of the Indian job market. As part of the process, an institution may initiate a session with the faculties or the students. The process adheres to the following rules :

1. Criticism is ruled out – No adverse judgments are allowed at the initial stage
2. Free-willing is welcome – The wilder the idea the easier it is to be modified
3. Quantity is wanted – More ideas facilitate better choices
4. Combination and improvement – Ideas of one may help others to generate another better idea.

The Process : Brainstorming involves the following steps :

Step I –

Introduce the purpose, i.e., defining the desired future of the institution in four sentences. Set a time scale like 20 –30 minutes. A short time span reduces wastage in talking and raises the energy levels. Select a recorder and set up a flipchart to record the ideas.

Step II –

Clarify and write down the values that you share in pursuing that vision. Different ideas do not have to be a problem. People can spur each other on to more daring and valuable dreams and visions -- dreams of changing the world that they are willing to work hard for.

Step III

Allow everyone to participate – start with each team member contributing in sequence, but allow people to pass. Encourage the team to have fun – to laugh with the wild ideas not at them. Record all ideas generated. Stop immediately after the end of the allotted time.

Weaknesses : According to Plsek (2000, pp.123 -127) the major weaknesses of brainstorming are as under :

1. While suspension of judgment and going for quantity is necessary for creative thinking, this is not sufficient,
2. As practiced today, brainstorming sessions naively assume that no prior preparation is needed. But, preparation is required in case of directed – creativity cycles like vision defining.

3. Brainstorming exhorts the participants to creativity but fails to describe how to achieve it. The method fails to provide clues regarding how to get novel ideas in the first place.

Despite these criticisms, this proves to be a good way of combining traditional with new and diverse ideas. Participants selected from the stakeholder groups for the brainstorming sessions must be notified well in advance, provided with the required study materials and requested to do a little homework to be capable of contributing valid ideas.

(3) Focus Groups

Focus group refers to a carefully planned discussion session designed for obtaining perceptions on a well-defined area of interest in a participative, permissive and non-threatening environment. This qualitative data collection technique is extremely valuable for obtaining naturalistic insights or ideas. With this technique, the evaluator identifies a particular group of individuals who meet certain criteria (e.g., members of the academic community). The individuals are brought together to discuss aspects of the topic at hand. The session typically lasts one to two hours, and is conducted in a conference room setting, with a moderator and a note-taker from the study team participating in the session. Success of a focus group discussion depends on careful selection of participants – seven to ten people are considered optimal – and homogeneity is always desirable. The group may be asked identical questions so that answers could be compared and evaluated. Homogeneous groups provide greater depth in a particular issue. Heterogeneous groups attained more shared meaning and respect among individuals. Participants answer specific questions and provide rich insight and hindsight. Invitations to participate in a focus group should be sent well in advance. The invitation must describe the purpose of the discussion, the requirements of the institution, the process that is to be followed during the discussion and some sample questions. A focus group session differs from a group interview in that participants in a focus group are encouraged to make contributions to the discussion beyond simply answering the moderator's questions. The moderator should have a short list of questions to ask during the session, but these questions should be broad. And the moderator should allow participants to bring up related issues.

The major weakness of focus groups is that it tends to generate a one-way flow of information, participants to the facilitator without actively involving or empowering the participants on the issues they are discussing. Focus groups have the potential to generate interests of the participants in the visioning process.

(4) Scenario Development

An interesting, but underutilized vision defining technique is scenario development. This can be done either as a group or an individual process. The basic idea with this approach is to have participants discuss what if... types of questions and construct scenarios, or likely series of events, that would need to occur if a particular vision or goal is to be accomplished. Scenario development is an especially useful technique for having participants consider possible future events, speculate about what key assumptions may drive the development of future events, and suggest the necessary elements for success in a particular scenario.

There are a number of methods for using scenario development as a successful data collection technique. One approach is to first carefully define the nature of the scenario to be explored, develop a one-page written description of an example scenario to use with the group (making sure it is pre-tested and revised before use), and identify appropriate topics and questions that need to be explored. Given the scenario, a number of discussion questions might be used with a group: e.g., what new courses could be

introduced, how would the institution collaborate with other institutions, how to assure campus placements, etc.

The views of group participants when discussing the implications and assumptions for a scenario can provide very useful insights into what users think might, or should, happen in the future. From the evaluator's point of view, these insights can be used to identify issues and strategies that might be helpful in designing the final vision statement. Facilitators must be careful to choose the appropriate individuals to participate in scenario development. Some training may be necessary for the moderator.

(5) Critical Incident Technique

To better understand users' perspectives, sometimes it is helpful to have users describe specific recent experiences or incidents related to the topic of the investigation. For example, the facilitator may ask the faculty to describe what will happen if the Government stops all kinds of grants to the educational institutions or what might happen if the student enrollment in an institution falls dramatically.

This technique is likely to provide more details about the consequences of reduction of grants or fall of enrollment than if the moderator simply asks what is the future of the educational institutions in general.

The critical incident technique may be used in an interview or in a survey. Once the respondent describes a specific experience or incident, the investigator may probe (in an interview) or ask a standard list of exploratory questions (in a survey). In an interview, the evaluator has much greater flexibility in probing and following up on specific experiences or incidents than in a survey. The critical incident technique is an excellent approach for focusing a user's attention on a particular type of experience or incident and is useful for capturing the rich details of the experience or incident.

Summing up

Summits are used to synthesize information gathered up to a certain date. Much of it is fragmented or incomplete in nature from which the final vision statement emerges. Typically, this kind of meeting is held at the end of the visioning effort. Participants of the summit meetings are provided with the themes, common ideas, and visions of previous efforts – the draft resolutions, proposals, future scenarios, trend projection, impact networks, etc. A writing group then refines the work of the summit group. This convergent process is time-consuming and sometimes very tedious especially when it becomes necessary to select one vision from among alternatives that are equally adoptable.

So far the concept of vision has been illustrated in the context of educational institutions in West Bengal. Institutions must have visions and visionaries. But the higher education system as a whole comprises many more individuals and institutions who directly or indirectly influence the major policy directives. Hence, visions developed within the four walls of the institutions will remain mere statements unless they are being absorbed in their true perspectives by the external regulatory authorities.

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